

QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN A VALUE PROPOSAL: FROM STANDARDS TO COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE.

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Relevance of the Study: Currently, many organizations strive to outperform their competitors. There are numerous ways to achieve this, such as lowering pricing or studying the strengths and weaknesses of competitors. However, often, after an organization has surpassed a competitor, the main challenge becomes establishing a sustainable market position, and this requires a system that creates value for the customer. This system is a quality management system, which can become a company's key competitive advantage. After all, if all processes are properly structured and operate smoothly, and employees understand their responsibilities, then high-quality products will be produced. This approach is key to creating a strong value proposition—the promise a company makes to its customers. Therefore, it is important to study the quality management system and the mechanics of its implementation within an organization.

Keywords: Quality management system, value proposition, competitive advantage, standardization, customer loyalty, transformation model, ISO 9001, PDCA cycle.

The purpose of this study is to examine how a quality management system can create a competitive advantage by leveraging a value proposition and understanding customer needs.

Research objectives:

- explain what a value proposition is, how it relates to quality, and why it is an important component.
- analyze and illustrate with examples how a quality management system (QMS) can help win customers over.
- develop and describe a model: "A Multi-Level Model for Transforming a QMS into a Competitive Advantage."

Results: The study analyzed the relationship between the value proposition and the quality management system, and developed a "Multi-Level Model for Transforming a QMS into a Competitive Advantage."

A value proposition is a clear definition of the key benefits a product or service provides to customers. It provides the key answer to the question of why a consumer should choose this product over a competitor [3]. When studying the concept of "Value Proposition," we can identify the following components: defining a problem or need for the target audience; describing the unique benefits the product offers customers; the stated value proposition must be provable and supported by customer reviews and opinions; the value proposition must be succinctly formulated so that every customer can understand and remember it; also, the desired product quality can vary significantly across different audience segments, so it is essential that the proposition be targeted [3]. An employer brand value proposition should answer two key questions: "What does this offer mean to me as an employee or candidate?" and "What can your company offer compared to others in the labor market?" During our research, we discovered that the value proposition and the quality management system are interrelated. Thus, while a value proposition articulates the specific benefits and expectations a company guarantees to its customers, a QMS represents the organizational and process mechanism that ensures the actual fulfillment of these obligations. Thus, a value proposition serves as a strategic guideline for the QMS, setting quality targets that are meaningful from the customer's perspective.

A quality management system (QMS) is not just an internal regulation, but also a marketing and customer relationship management (CRM) tool. Its impact occurs in three key areas: Reducing cognitive load and risk for the client (standardized processes guarantee predictable results, thereby reducing customer anxiety); Building an emotional connection through care (when the QMS incorporates a PDCA [2] cycle based on feedback, the client feels valued and their problems are addressed, strengthening their trust); Creating a positive social identity (consuming products or services from a company with an excellent reputation becomes part of the client's self-identification).

We decided to study companies that use QMS to attract clients. T-Bank and Toyota were used as case studies.

At T-Bank, QMS tools are integrated into the digital ecosystem with the goal of continuously improving the service's value for the client. The basis of this approach is the systematic collection and analysis of big data on user behavior. Every action in the mobile app, every call center request, and every transaction is recorded and becomes input for future improvement processes. In practice, this is achieved through regular cycles of reviewing and optimizing the customer experience. For example, feedback mechanisms such as simplified post-service surveys allow for near-real-time assessment of satisfaction and prompt adjustments. Thus, T-Bank's QMS functions as a dynamic system that transforms raw data on customer

behavior into specific service improvements. This creates a user-friendly and intuitive bank for consumers, one that considers their needs and quickly adapts to them.

Toyota demonstrates a different approach, shifting the focus from the digital ecosystem to the production culture. The primary tool here is the Toyota Production System (TPS), which embodies principles that extend beyond the shop floor. Two of these principles play a key role: Jidoka (automation with an element of human intelligence) and Kaizen (continuous improvement). For the customer, this translates into tangible values such as unparalleled reliability, high residual value, and a sense of security. The Toyota brand becomes synonymous with these qualities, fostering not just loyalty but genuine commitment based on rational trust and decades of positive operating experience. Thus, an analysis of T-Bank and Toyota's practices shows that there is no single approach to using a quality management system to influence customers. But the key is that systematic quality management directly translates into competitive advantages, expressed in customer loyalty and a strengthened market position.

A Multi-Level Model for Transforming a Quality Management System into a Competitive Advantage

Based on literature review and other sources, we developed a "Multi-Level Model for Transforming a Quality Management System into a Competitive Advantage." The core idea is that the quality management system is divided into three levels, arranged in a pyramid, enabling the company to achieve its goals of attracting and retaining customers and increasing profits.

Figure 1 - Multilevel Model

The model consists of several levels: at the first level, the company strives to stabilize the management of key business processes by creating a unified system. This includes the development and implementation of organizational and regulatory documents: quality policies, guidelines, procedures, and instructions. Best practices are identified, which allows for

standardization of work and makes it accessible to the entire organization. Successful completion of this level is confirmed by certification, for example, ISO 9001 [1], which serves as proof of the system's reliability to external parties. At the second level, a transition to a value-based approach to quality management occurs. This means that the company focuses not on standards, but on creating excellence in the customer's perception, making the QMS a tool for implementing strategy. The main principle is a focus on customer needs, which requires a shift in emphasis from internal regulations to external expectations. At the second level, the QMS is used to create a unique value proposition through continuous process improvement, such as the PDCA cycle [2]. This results in a strong value proposition that evokes emotional loyalty and positive brand associations, turning quality into a powerful marketing asset. The third level of the model is the advantage level. Here, quality becomes part of the corporate culture, and the company declares, "We are chosen for our uniqueness." Maintaining high quality becomes the norm for all employees. A strong brand is formed, associated with reliability, innovation, or premium service. This creates high switching costs for customers, who remain even with more favorable offers from competitors. The company sets market standards, attracting specialists and loyal supporters. Customers feel protected and confident. Quality expenditures are transformed into strategic assets, generating value for the business and customers.

Company management can use this model as an analytical tool.

Conclusions: This study analyzed the relationship between the value proposition and the QMS, illustrated with examples how the QMS allows organizations to position their customers, and developed a "Multi-Level Model for Transforming the QMS into a Competitive Advantage," which will be useful for organizations in analyzing their operations.

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